

Supplementary Information for

Heart Rate Variability during Head-Up Tilt shows inter-individual differences among healthy individuals of extreme *Prakriti* types

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Supplementary figures

Figure S1: Overall representation (of Cohort 1) of differences of HR and HRV parameters in *Prakriti* specific manner showing significance level and directionality in different stages of HUT test. Directionality is for first group as compared to second group

Abbreviations: Base, Baseline; CSI, Cardiac Sympathetic Index; CVI, Cardiac Vagal Index; HF, high frequency; LF, low frequency; LF/HF, LF and HF ratio; nu, normalized unit; pNN50, percentage of NN50; RMSSD, root mean square of successive R-R interval differences; SampEn, Sample Entropy; SD1, standard deviation of instantaneous beat-to-beat variability; SD2, standard deviation of long-term beat to-beat variability; SDNN, standard deviation of normal to normal R-R intervals; Tidx, Triangular Index; %Δ1, relative change from supine to tilt; %Δ2, relative change from tilt to resupine.

Figure S2: Overall representation (of Cohort 2) of differences of HR and HRV parameters in Prakriti specific manner showing significance level and directionality in different stages of HUT test. Directionality is for first group as compared to second group

Abbreviations: Base, Baseline; CSI, Cardiac Sympathetic Index; CVI, Cardiac Vagal Index; HF, high frequency; LF, low frequency; LF/HF, LF and HF ratio; nu, normalized unit; pNN50, percentage of NN50; RMSSD, root mean square of successive R-R interval differences; SampEn, Sample Entropy; SD1, standard deviation of instantaneous beat-to-beat variability; SD2, standard deviation of long-term beat to-beat variability; SDNN, standard deviation of normal to normal R-R intervals; Tidx, Triangular Index; %Δ1, relative change from supine to tilt; %Δ2, relative change from tilt to resupine.

Figure S3: Line plots showing trends in Time and Frequency domain parameters of HRV among *Prakriti* groups at different phases of HUT test

Abbreviations: bpm, beats per minute; HF, high frequency; LF, low frequency; LF/HF, LF and HF ratio; nu, normalized unit; pNN50, percentage of NN50; RMSSD, root mean square of successive R-R interval differences; SDNN, standard deviation of normal to normal R-R intervals; Tidx, Triangular Index

Figure S4: Line plots showing trends in non-linear parameters of HRV among *Prakriti* groups at different phases of HUT test

Abbreviations: CSI, Cardiac Sympathetic Index; CVI, Cardiac Vagal Index; SD1, standard deviation of instantaneous beat-to-beat variability; SD2, standard deviation of long-term beat to-beat variability; SampEn, Sample Entropy;

Figure S5: Validation of HRV differences amongst four *Prakriti* groups through analysis of significance performed in 10000 random iterations of same parent dataset. The dot plot showing the p-values of 10000 randomized comparisons of HRV parameters where red dot indicates original p-value of the comparison between *Vata*, *Pitta*, *Kapha* and Mixed groups and the green line indicates top 5% cut-off of permuted p-values.

Abbreviations: CSI, Cardiac Sympathetic Index; HF, high frequency; LF, low frequency; LF/HF, LF and HF ratio; nu, normalized unit; RMSSD, root mean square of successive R-R interval differences; SD1, standard deviation of instantaneous beat-to-beat variability; SD2, standard deviation of long-term beat to-beat variability; SDR: SD1/SD2; SampEn, Sample Entropy; %Δ1, relative change from supine to tilt; %Δ2, relative change from tilt to resupine

Supplementary Tables

Table S1: Heart rate variability indices (absolute values) in different *Prakriti* groups at baseline (supine) without Bonferroni Correction

Parameters	<i>Vata</i> (n=97)	<i>Pitta</i> (n=68)	<i>Kapha</i> (n=68)	Mixed (n=146)	<i>p</i> -value
Heart Rate(bpm)	68.51 (61.65-81.43)	70.535 (64.4-77.45)	72.265 (66.06-80.82)	70.78 (62.93-78.42)	0.446
Time domain					
SDNN(ms)	48.52 (34.39-64.63)	47.36 (36.77-60.4)	42.14 (31.57-53.86)	45.905 (33.42-66.28)	0.237
RMSSD(ms)	44.99 (31.28-59.96)	41.42 (27.63-55.72)	39.63 (23.93-57.89)	41.315 (27.21-62.53)	0.568
pNN50	27.21 (8.35-41.03)	20.41 (5.61-37.69)	19.825 (2.95-39.69)	17.23 (4.81-45.07)	0.488
Geometric domain					
Tidx	11.21 (9.62-15.35)	11.73 (9.61-15.25)	10.4 (8.27-12.78)	11.475 (9.11-15.07)	0.085 ^{a,b}
Frequency domain					
LF (ms²)	424.48 (243.08-807.78)	518.805 (321.56-764.08)	380.67 (193.19-697.74)	493.38 (246.15-934.98)	0.348
HF (ms²)	482.2 (277.62-1061.76)	499.05 (245.38-826.18)	355.035 (125.32-729.7)	454.5 (197.84-1126.44)	0.101 ^{a, c}
LF (nu)	47.37 (29.91-59.66)	47.765 (40.58-59.96)	54.725 (42.11-66.27)	49.56 (38-63.2)	0.146 ^a
HF (nu)	49.64 (38.34-64.52)	47.145 (36.32-56.61)	42.615 (31.09-54.57)	46.91 (33.63-57.87)	0.105 ^a
Total Power (ms²)	1495.8 (818.44-2868.4)	1417.51 (968.37-3117.31)	1088.895 (670.31-2136.67)	1476.91 (711.79-2833.51)	0.168 ^b

LF/HF	0.92 (0.47-1.49)	1 (0.7-1.63)	1.29 (0.75-2.05)	1.04 (0.7-1.85)	0.106 ^a
Non-linear analysis					
SD1 (ms)	31.86 (22.14-42.44)	29.33 (19.83-39.47)	28.07 (16.85-40.93)	29.045 (19.29-44.87)	0.532
SD2 (ms)	58.86 (40.83-80.14)	58.895 (48.03-71.64)	52.195 (41.48-64.36)	56.325 (42.19-79.3)	0.127 ^{a,b,c}
SDR	0.52 (0.46-0.63)	0.485 (0.38-0.65)	0.555 (0.42-0.66)	0.5 (0.4-0.63)	0.297
CSI	1.91 (1.58-2.18)	2.065 (1.54-2.63)	1.795 (1.51-2.4)	2 (1.59-2.48)	0.307
CVI	4.48 (4.17-4.69)	4.46 (4.16-4.63)	4.35 (4.05-4.6)	4.465 (4.12-4.77)	0.302
SampEn	1.66 (1.48-1.82)	1.635 (1.47-1.84)	1.69 (1.46-1.85)	1.63 (1.45-1.78)	0.733

Note: Values are expressed as median (interquartile range).

Abbreviations: BPM, beats per minutes; CSI, Cardiac Sympathetic Index; CVI, Cardiac Vagal Index; HF, high frequency; LF, low frequency; LF/HF, LF and HF ratio; ms, millisecond; nu, normalized unit; pNN50, percentage of NN50; RMSSD, root mean square of successive R-R interval differences; SampEn, Sample Entropy; SD1, standard deviation of instantaneous beat-to-beat variability; SD2, standard deviation of long-term beat to-beat variability; SDR, SD1/SD2 ratio; SDNN, standard deviation of normal to normal R-R intervals; Tidx, Triangular Index; a, *Vata* compared to *Kapha*; b, *Kapha* compared to *Pitta*; c, *Kapha* compared to Mixed; * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$; **** $p < 0.0001$; * $\exists$ {a,b,c}.

Table S2: The Heart rate variability indices (absolute values) among different *Prakriti* groups in Tilt Phase

Parameters	<i>Vata</i> (n=97)	<i>Pitta</i> (n=68)	<i>Kapha</i> (n=68)	Mixed (n=146)	<i>p</i> -value
Heart Rate	83.79 (73.85-98.15)	85.47 (77.69-93.75)	83.17 (76.94-91.39)	84.735 (76.2525-92.665)	0.767
Time domain					
SDNN	44.79 (34.62-57.01)	51.28 (40.78-65.45)	42.92 (31.44-52.52)	43.175 (33.7225-60.8425)	0.023 ^b
RMSSD	22.71 (15.61-30.02)	23.12 (16.52-33.39)	25.43 (15.76-35.65)	21.735 (16.195-30.9225)	0.633

pNN50	2.75 (0.88-7.82)	3.8 (0.9-9.68)	3.76 (0.65-14.65)	2.585 (0.7675-8.1625)	0.772
Geometric domain					
Tidx	10.45 (8.15-13.2768)	12.59 (9.53-14.31)	9.94 (7.43-12.58)	10.8455 (8.252225-13.31)	0.017 ^b
Frequency domain					
LF	358.26 (202.87-760.39)	564.16 (348.75-965.03)	375.73 (203.89-747.95)	455.73 (259.085-932.1325)	0.042
HF	157.78 (79.41-359.96)	205.39 (92.49-332.58)	192.9 (81.14-513.67)	191.085 (104.74-337.41)	0.605
LF(nu)	67.22 (55.93-79.45)	73.25 (56.17-82.38)	61.29 (50.47-73.24)	70.515 (54.0375-79.7325)	0.110
HF(nu)	27.87 (15.36-40.92)	23.3 (13.3-36.76)	34.92 (24.27-45.76)	26.825 (16.77-42.5)	0.022 ^b
Total Power	1151.87 (633.52-1846.24)	1552.32 (851.52-2318.43)	978.02 (601.21-1680.69)	1217.01 (694.47-2257.07)	0.027 ^b
LF/HF	2.43 (1.42-4.62)	3.14 (1.62-5.92)	1.83 (1.09-3.04)	2.725 (1.265-4.71)	0.034 ^b
Non-linear analysis					
SD1	16.11 (11.06-21.4)	16.51 (11.72-22.97)	17.56 (11.16-25.27)	15.37 (11.55-21.92)	0.691
SD2	61.51 (47.67-77.63)	71.05 (54.49-89.02)	56.36 (42.87-72.33)	59.79 (45.3775-83.1125)	0.016 ^b
SDR	0.25 (0.21-0.32)	0.23 (0.19-0.3)	0.31 (0.24-0.39)	0.26 (0.21-0.37)	0.001 ^{a, bb}
CSI	3.96 (3.1-4.79)	4.32 (3.3-5.37)	3.2 (2.59-4.12)	3.86 (2.7125-4.7075)	0.001 ^{a, b}
CVI	4.19 (3.92-4.42)	4.26 (4.08-4.47)	4.2 (3.92-4.41)	4.17 (3.9725-4.4375)	0.449
SampEn	1.16 (0.86-1.4)	1.07 (0.76-1.28)	1.3 (1.06-1.53)	1.245 (1.0125-1.4875)	0.001 ^{bb, d}

Note: Values are expressed as median (interquartile range).

Abbreviations: BPM, beats per minutes; CSI, Cardiac Sympathetic Index; CVI, Cardiac Vagal Index; HF, high frequency; LF, low frequency; LF/HF, LF and HF ratio; ms, millisecond; nu, normalized unit; pNN50, percentage of NN50; RMSSD, root mean square of successive R-R interval differences; SampEn, Sample Entropy; SD1, standard deviation of instantaneous beat-to-beat variability; SD2, standard deviation of long-term beat to-beat variability; SDR, SD1/SD2 ratio; SDNN, standard deviation of normal to normal R-R intervals; Tidx, Triangular Index; a, *Vata* compared to *Kapha*; b, *Kapha* compared to *Pitta*; c, *Kapha* compared to Mixed; d, *Pitta* compared to Mixed; * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$; **** $p < 0.0001$; * $\exists$ {a,b,c,d}.

Table S3: The Heart rate variability indices (absolute values) among different *Prakriti* groups in Resupine Phase

Parameters	<i>Vata</i> (n=97)	<i>Pitta</i> (n=68)	<i>Kapha</i> (n=68)	Mixed (n=146)	<i>p</i> -value
Heart Rate	67.33 (61.14-78.18)	70.32 (64.14-75.11)	72.85 (65.62-79.28)	70.27 (61.93-76.99)	0.250
Time domain					
SDNN	57.25 (46.77-76.36)	58.65 (44.1-74.67)	54.53 (35.81-69.01)	60.15 (42.48-76.2)	0.329
RMSSD	49.34 (34.63-63.35)	45.7 (34.45-59.6)	42.89 (26.17-59.91)	45.99 (30.09-66.59)	0.296
pNN50	30.4 (13.79-47.23)	25.71 (12.8-41.71)	21.61 (3.79-43.63)	24.72 (7.13-46.92)	0.174
Geometric domain					
Tidx	13.61 (10.9013-17)	14.56 (11.07-18.73)	12.15 (8.97-15.8)	14.42 (10.42-17.78)	0.034 ^b
Frequency domain					
LF	451.16 (265.62-886.54)	498.16 (335.49-795.54)	390.76 (184.38-757.22)	546.6 (263.17-1005.13)	0.286
HF	549.81 (298.2-1092.12)	570.08 (257.67-892.77)	337.94 (150.26-738.08)	490.67 (250.68-1177.73)	0.038 ^a
LF(nu)	44.78 (32.94-57.23)	47.02 (35.84-58.96)	53.69 (42.9-64.27)	48.26 (38.11-61.51)	0.077
HF(nu)	50.68 (34.86-63.6)	45.14 (34.31-56.33)	42.94 (29.79-52.87)	47.23 (33.01-58.31)	0.049 ^a
Total Power	1734.63 (1033.64-2835.42)	1755.01 (1109.55-3135.75)	1284.21 (607.53-2897.79)	1894.27 (892.53-2947.59)	0.141

LF/HF	0.97 (0.55-1.68)	1.07 (0.65-1.73)	1.33 (0.87-2.06)	0.99 (0.67-1.89)	0.053 ^a
Non-linear analysis					
SD1	35.04 (24.52-45.68)	32.37 (24.41-42.27)	29.86 (18.54-42.43)	32.57 (21.66-47.14)	0.281
SD2	72.78 (57.66-91.68)	75.99 (57.4-94.11)	65.65 (46.68-88.18)	76.58 (55.03-99.37)	0.248
SDR	0.49 (0.37-0.6)	0.44 (0.34-0.53)	0.44 (0.36-0.53)	0.44 (0.34-0.56)	0.218
CSI	2.05 (1.66-2.69)	2.29 (1.91-2.92)	2.3 (1.89-2.78)	2.29 (1.79-2.95)	0.219
CVI	4.62 (4.35-4.85)	4.58 (4.38-4.82)	4.5 (4.11-4.72)	4.62 (4.29-4.83)	0.289
SampEn	1.56 (1.36-1.75)	1.54 (1.36-1.71)	1.54 (1.37-1.76)	1.55 (1.35-1.7)	0.895

Note: Values are expressed as median (interquartile range).

Abbreviations: BPM, beats per minutes; CSI, Cardiac Sympathetic Index; CVI, Cardiac Vagal Index; HF, high frequency; LF, low frequency; LF/HF, LF and HF ratio; ms, millisecond; nu, normalized unit; pNN50, percentage of NN50; RMSSD, root mean square of successive R-R interval differences; SampEn, Sample Entropy; SD1, standard deviation of instantaneous beat-to-beat variability; SD2, standard deviation of long-term beat to-beat variability; SDR, SD1/SD2 ratio; SDNN, standard deviation of normal to normal R-R intervals; Tidx, Triangular Index; a, *Vata* compared to *Kapha*; b, *Kapha* compared to *Pitta*; c, *Kapha* compared to Mixed; d, *Pitta* compared to Mixed; * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$; **** $p < 0.0001$

Table S4: The Heart rate variability indices among Mixed *Prakriti* groups at baseline (rest in supine position)

Baseline				
Parameters	Kapha-Pitta (n=51)	Vata-Kapha (n=13)	Vata-Pitta (n=82)	P-value
Heart Rate(bpm)	70.87(62.66-77.92)	70.36(65.22-72.08)	71.93(62.61-79.05)	0.607
Time domain				
SDNN (ms)	43.41(30.44-65.91)	41.23(32.13-70.6)	49.91(36.58-64.87)	0.459
RMSSD (ms)	36.19(26.22-57.04)	33.7(22.78-68.71)	47.71(29.52-65.64)	0.405

pNN50	16.02(5.1-32.32)	11.7(2.19-33.95)	25.98(8.26-46.77)	0.258
Geometric domain				
Tidx	10.84(8.47-14.24)	10.64(7.41-11.06)	12.91(9.68-15.93)	0.047
Frequency domain				
LF (ms²)	473.25(246.02-892)	389.83(271.2-888.28)	523.24(246.15-967.84)	0.888
HF (ms²)	411.27(189.98-982.74)	323.86(192.64-719.21)	578.66(235.41-1180.72)	0.308
LF (nu)	49.8(44.74-63.05)	59.81(41.2-67.54)	47.77(35.32-61.66)	0.135
HF (nu)	46(33.53-55.05)	40.19(32.46-58.8)	48.96(34.25-59.15)	0.579
Total Power (ms²)	1334.67(678.51-2423.17)	1276.93(586.66-3528.73)	1666.68(781.93-3072.69)	0.292
LF/HF	1.17(0.82-1.83)	1.49(0.7-2.08)	0.95(0.62-1.76)	0.310
Non-linear analysis				
SD1 (ms)	25.63(18.58-40.39)	23.86(16.13-48.66)	33.79(20.91-46.49)	0.405
SD2 (ms)	55.2(38.46-82.95)	53.61(42.55-81.12)	58.27(47.14-77.54)	0.603
SDR	0.5(0.42-0.61)	0.52(0.39-0.61)	0.5(0.39-0.66)	0.930
CSI	2(1.65-2.37)	1.93(1.63-2.58)	2.01(1.52-2.58)	0.927
CVI	4.37(4.08-4.75)	4.34(4.04-4.72)	4.51(4.15-4.77)	0.525
SampEn	1.71(1.52-1.84)	1.72(1.48-1.87)	1.59(1.43-1.72)	0.049

Note: Values are expressed as median (interquartile range).

Abbreviations: BPM, beats per minutes; CSI, Cardiac Sympathetic Index; CVI, Cardiac Vagal Index; HF, high frequency; LF, low frequency; LF/HF, LF and HF ratio; ms, millisecond; nu, normalized unit; pNN50, percentage of NN50; RMSSD, root mean square of successive R-R interval differences; SampEn, Sample Entropy; SD1, standard deviation of instantaneous beat-to-beat variability; SD2, standard deviation of long-term beat to-beat variability; SDR, SD1/SD2 ratio; SDNN, standard deviation of normal to normal R-R intervals; Tidx, Triangular Index;

Table S5: The relative change (% Δ_I) of Heart Rate Variability indices among Mixed Prakriti groups in response to orthostatic stress than supine to tilt position

Parameters	Kapha-Pitta (n=51)	Vata-Kapha (n=13)	Vata-Pitta (n=82)	P-value
% Δ_I Heart Rate	12.99(6.61-19.27)	14.57(11.26-17.6)	17.28(10.19-30.87)	0.035 ^a
Time domain				
% Δ_I SDNN	3.27(-21.88-27.3)	9.51(-5.78-14.45)	-7.6(-30.71-24.14)	0.415
% Δ_I RMSSD	-35.38(-49.69--22.46)	-21.83(-48.9--17.56)	-47.7(-67.62--26.05)	0.041
% Δ_I pNN50	-77.78(-90.79--46.43)	-32.74(-80.2--19.44)	-83.51(-97.89--60.65)	0.012 ^b
Geometric domain				
% Δ_I Tidx	2.64(-16.78-15.96)	7.4(-16.47-20.72)	-14.46(-32.49-16.44)	0.249
Frequency domain				
% Δ_I LF	5.15(-36.31-53.33)	31.07(-28.36-71.41)	-8.25(-44.34-74.05)	0.767
% Δ_I HF	-44.36(-68.74--6.17)	-26.75(-67.29-10.07)	-63.5(-84.88--30.31)	0.019 ^a
% Δ_I LF(nu)	17.05(-2.13-47.76)	14.04(4.66-29.62)	44.71(11.01-86.6)	0.025 ^a
% Δ_I HF(nu)	-22.33(-50.07-1.84)	-37.71(-55.91--16.8)	-47.58(-67.24--16.28)	0.045 ^a
% Δ_I Total Power	-3.19(-37.35-31.6)	13.69(-27.8-25.62)	-23.92(-47.8-29.18)	0.502
% Δ_I LF/HF	61.81(-4.97-263.76)	93.51(25.83-212.69)	201.86(33.63-456.19)	0.042 ^a
Non-linear analysis				
% Δ_I SD1	-35.33(-49.67--22.4)	-21.82(-48.87--17.42)	-46.93(-67.6--25.93)	0.045
% Δ_I SD2	8.14(-13.14-39.16)	11.36(-4.08-20.19)	1.71(-19.1-36.24)	0.642
% Δ_I SDR	-40(-53.58--27.82)	-35.9(-49.18--25.93)	-50.49(-59.14--29.23)	0.089

$\%A_1$ CSI	64.86(40.32-114.59)	53.49(34.97-100)	99.9(42.66-145.01)	0.081
$\%A_1$ CVI	-3.54(-8.08-0.83)	-0.99(-3.71--0.27)	-5.32(-12.33--0.47)	0.083
$\%A_1$ SampEn	-18.71(-31--4.29)	-17.78(-34.43--6.81)	-19.82(-41.2--7.34)	0.653

Note: Values are expressed as median (interquartile range).

Abbreviations: BPM, beats per minutes; CSI, Cardiac Sympathetic Index; CVI, Cardiac Vagal Index; HF, high frequency; LF, low frequency; LF/HF, LF and HF ratio; ms, millisecond; nu, normalized unit; pNN50, percentage of NN50; RMSSD, root mean square of successive R-R interval differences; SampEn, Sample Entropy; SD1, standard deviation of instantaneous beat-to-beat variability; SD2, standard deviation of long-term beat to-beat variability; SDR, SD1/SD2 ratio; SDNN, standard deviation of normal to normal R-R intervals; Tidx, Triangular Index; a, *Kapha-Pitta* compared to *Vata-Pitta*; b, *Vata-Pitta* compared to *Vata-Kapha*; * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$; **** $p < 0.0001$

Table S6: The relative change ($\%A_2$) of Heart Rate Variability indices among Mixed Prakriti groups during recovery response than tilt to resupine position

Parameters	Kapha-Pitta (n=51)	Vata-Kapha (n=13)	Vata-Pitta (n=82)	P-value
$\%A_2$ Heart Rate	-12.97(-18.16--6.39)	-10.2(-12.24--9.74)	-16.49(-24.61--11.71)	0.003 ^{a,b}
Time domain				
$\%A_2$ SDNN	18.33(-7.43-59.28)	34.54(12.64-54)	34.94(6.54-76.78)	0.195
$\%A_2$ RMSSD	62.09(19.19-125.7)	60.97(44.22-109.9)	124.83(57.33-198.95)	0.005 ^{aa}
$\%A_2$ pNN50	340.1(64.68-1188.21)	386.18(90.58-634.15)	436.9(181.04-1397.62)	0.431
Geometric domain				
$\%A_2$ Tidx	13.14(-4.93-44.81)	23.26(13-40.19)	35.3(10.74-67.82)	0.038 ^a
Frequency domain				
$\%A_2$ LF	2.98(-38.35-103.03)	37.04(-46.15-58.25)	13.66(-33.71-90.17)	0.961
$\%A_2$ HF	83.42(15.8-265.58)	81.46(20.99-249.12)	237.41(55.3-486.59)	0.011 ^a
$\%A_2$ LF(nu)	-18.38(-34.09--0.86)	-19.82(-36.93-2.67)	-30.82(-47.95--7.33)	0.042

%Δ_2 HF(nu)	37.77(-0.12-93.38)	75.74(-6.46-113.73)	81.99(10.79-248.47)	0.037 ^a
%Δ_2 Total Power	23.64(-15.24-128.85)	69.41(-13.99-107.13)	37.45(-4.76-96.07)	0.679
%Δ_2 LF/HF	-41.06(-66.54-0.4)	-57.84(-69.33-10.96)	-65.42(-85.15--16)	0.022 ^a
Non-linear analysis				
%Δ_2 SD1	59.86(19.09-125.35)	60.86(44.18-109.81)	123.4(56.83-199.36)	0.005 ^{aa}
%Δ_2 SD2	9.2(-11.25-53.93)	29.87(8.75-50.08)	24.42(-3.27-68.19)	0.287
%Δ_2 SDR	37.84(15.21-88)	32(10-55)	76.44(27.14-134.58)	0.040
%Δ_2 CSI	-27.49(-45.96--12.47)	-23.48(-35.02--7.07)	-43.01(-56.48--21.97)	0.035
%Δ_2 CVI	6.03(1.41-12.18)	7.73(4.62-11.97)	10.27(5.59-16.16)	0.020 ^a
%Δ_2 SampEn	14.06(1.89-40.22)	6.45(-6.8-22.64)	21.2(-2.9-70.37)	0.317

Note: Values are expressed as median (interquartile range).

Abbreviations: BPM, beats per minutes; CSI, Cardiac Sympathetic Index; CVI, Cardiac Vagal Index; HF, high frequency; LF, low frequency; LF/HF, LF and HF ratio; ms, millisecond; nu, normalized unit; pNN50, percentage of NN50; RMSSD, root mean square of successive R-R interval differences; SampEn, Sample Entropy; SD1, standard deviation of instantaneous beat-to-beat variability; SD2, standard deviation of long-term beat to-beat variability; SDR, SD1/SD2 ratio; SDNN, standard deviation of normal to normal R-R intervals; Tidx, Triangular Index; a, *Kapha-Pitta* compared to *Vata-Pitta*; b, *Vata-Pitta* compared to *Vata-Kapha*; * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$; **** $p < 0.0001$